

**PRINCIPLES OF TEACHING CREATIVE THINKING IN
ELEMENTARY STUDENTS IN THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL
PROCESS**

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Abstract: The relevance of this article is that we are implementing the model of developed countries in the educational process. In the process of studying them, it was observed that non-traditionalism in education, interesting activities that encourage students to think logically and creatively were carried out. As an example, let's take the Pisa curriculum, which we began to implement in education, and these are discussed in detail.

Keywords: Logical education of students, model, logic, creative, training, test, thought, knowledge, Pisa curriculum.

Introduction:

It is through this program that the country's potential in the field of education, its achievements and shortcomings are determined. The important aspect of this is that if freedom and diversity of opinions are implemented in the educational process, this will quickly give results. During the years of independence, fundamental reforms were carried out in the field of education in our country. In particular, our first President I.A. Karimov paid special attention to this area and said: "We need to pay more attention to our scientists and creative workers. Because it is they who create spiritual wealth. Taking care of them, creating all the necessary material and spiritual conditions for effective activity, is the duty and responsibility of the heads of state authorities and economic organizations." Indeed, only when creative people are given free opportunities can they make various inventions. If we look at history, during the authoritarian regime, creative thinkers, statesmen,

and “enemies of the people” were repressed. Many of our enlightened ancestors could not freely express their thoughts. As a result, the economy and education developed only one-sidedly.

When introducing free creativity in the field of education, we must start with the lower stage of education, preschool education. In recent years, special attention has been paid to this area. The establishment of the Ministry of Preschool Education is a vivid example of this. In this regard, it is appropriate to recall the following thoughts of our current President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev: "The first task is to openly recognize that we are neglecting work in this important area. The coverage of children in this area is 27 percent. According to the recently approved program, the material and technical base of 2,200 institutions in this area has been strengthened."

It is very important to develop the ability to think independently in a student at kindergarten age and give it the right direction. Therefore, if students are given exercises based on logical consistency in kindergarten education, it is of great importance for the student's development.

In recent years, great attention has been paid to school education in our country. In particular, the introduction of Presidential schools and private schools that meet world standards is a vivid example of this. It is in these educational institutions that practice and theory are integrally based on free thinking and creativity. Therefore, children who study in such schools stand out. Also, the role of creativity in higher education, which is the highest level of education, is extremely incomparable. It is enough to recall the following about the opportunities created in higher education. “A new, improved system has been introduced for the regular retraining of professors of higher educational institutions in the field of higher education. In 15 basic higher educational institutions, retraining and advanced training courses for teachers and heads of higher educational institutions were organized. About 2,700 students of higher educational institutions improved their skills in these courses.

These indicators are indicators of higher education in the early period of

independence. Recently, reforms have been carried out in higher education in our country, as in all sectors. In particular, the encouragement of professors and teachers for scientific discoveries, an increase in their monthly salaries, and the further transparency of entrance exams in higher education are examples of this. In recent years, scientific and creative discoveries have been carried out in cooperation with developed higher educational institutions of the world. As a result, there is an increase in various scientific fields. Articles 41-42 of our Constitution, the main law of the republic, also mention the education system, support for free creativity and scientific discoveries. In particular, Article 41 states: “Everyone has the right to education. Free general education is guaranteed by the state. School affairs are under state control.”

It is clear from this that a great path has been opened in our country for scientific discoveries and knowledge. They are encouraged by the state. At the same time, these discoveries must be made for the development of the homeland and the well-being of the people. Scientific and technical discoveries that contradict progress and endanger human life will not be allowed and will be subject to criminal liability. The development of society is based on scientific research activities. If there are various studies in society, then there will be progress. The scientific and technological revolution that took place at the end of the 20th century is also a product of high creativity of people. [By this time, various studies have been created. In this regard, it is appropriate to recall the following thoughts of the philosopher: “Scientific research activities help a person to self-evaluate, that is, if a person wants to be a true scientist, he must control his passions and aspirations, make rational, effective and optimal decisions, and engage in heuristic activities that serve goodness. The result of such activities is manifested as discovery and creativity”

People who create such discoveries and creative products are usually called creative people. From this it can be seen that the product of creativity and creativity,

scientific and practical discoveries and inventions are the product of unconventional logical thinking. In our country, all conditions have been created and are being created for the development of science and technology and for people engaged in scientific research. This process is controlled by the Oliy Majlis and the Cabinet of Ministers. The following are examples of this. From the first days of Uzbekistan's independence, a lot of organizational and practical work has been carried out for the development of the field of science and technology. In particular: On February 18, 1992, the "Committee on Science and Technology" of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established. In accordance with the Resolution No. 77 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Organization of Scientific Research Activities" of February 20, 2002, the Council for the Coordination of Scientific and Technical Development was established under the auspices of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is clear from this that special attention is paid to this area in our country. After all, any society is based on the implementation of its laws. If we look at history, our great ancestors laid the foundation for world science. Ibn Sina, Beruni, Abu Nasr Farobi, Al-Khwarizmi, Mirzo Ulugbek, Alishar Navoi, Ahmad Ferghani, etc. created a kind of revolution in various fields of science. Our native land is one of the hotbeds of science.

Conclusion: The uniqueness of these great ancestors is that they were highly creative and logical thinkers. Today, in order to produce such great scientists, we have embarked on a new path of reforming the education sector. In conclusion, it should be said that creative thinking is important in all fields. Especially medical workers, lawyers, economists, architects, teachers, philosophers, etc. We will develop qualified personnel in all fields by developing the education sector. Therefore, special attention should be paid to this area. All types of teachers working in the education system must, first of all, be creative thinkers, have their own unique style and direction.

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